
68. Gaia photometry

WHILE GAIA'S EMPHATIC advance is its astrometry, the parallel acquisition of high-accuracy multi-epoch photometry for all stars is an enormously powerful complement. A survey of more than a billion stars, establishing how far they are away, and how they are moving through space, is of course a major advance. But without appropriate *photometric* information, there would be little indication of what these stars actually *are*.

In making the case for an expensive space mission, scientists cannot expect to execute from space what can be done from the ground. And multi-colour photometry *can* be acquired from the ground.

But there were compelling reasons to do this onboard. One was instrumental: significant chromatic displacements, due to asymmetric wavefront aberrations, can only be corrected if the star's colour is known.

From a scientific perspective, in a Universe in which variable stars abound, an unbiased astrometric survey must be based on stars selected according to their magnitude at each measurement epoch. Of similar importance, for statistical considerations, is that object selection should also be based on detection and thresholding at the same angular resolution as the astrometric measurements themselves.

The case for onboard photometry is compounded for transient sources such as supernovae, as well as for solar system objects moving rapidly across the sky.

MUCH EFFORT was devoted to such photometric optimisation. The two-colour photometry of Hipparcos could only hint as to each object's nature. Better data could distinguish spectral type and luminosity class, and stellar metallicity and interstellar extinction, all contributing to a more informed survey of our Galaxy.

Implementation wasn't trivial: using filter photometry, how many filters could be accommodated, and how could they be organised in the focal plane? Would every star have to be measured at each epoch in every filter? How should the fixed transit time at the focal-plane be divided up between high-accuracy (unfiltered) astrometry, and the diagnostic multi-colour photometry?

THE SCIENTIFIC BREADTH of Gaia is enormous, and multi-colour diagnostic photometry had to be optimised accordingly. With more than a billion parallaxes, Gaia is covering all phases of stellar evolution across the full range of stellar masses and populations, including pre-main-sequence stars, chemically peculiar stars, and a wide range of variable stars observed some 70 times during the nominal five-year operations phase.

Multi-colour photometry provides an important diagnostic for eclipsing binaries. And for the many tens of thousands of solar system objects, multi-colour photometry provides a decisive tool for taxonomy.

BOTH BEFORE AND AFTER mission selection by ESA in 2000, various groups devoted to specific aspects, worked together under the coordinating structure of the Gaia Science Team. Of relevance here was the Photometry Working Group, jointly led by Erik Høg (Copenhagen) and Carme Jordi (Barcelona). Many others contributed their expertise, their time, and their enthusiasm.

Amongst these were Jens Knude (Copenhagen), bringing his lifelong experience in photometry, especially concerning the intermediate-band Strömgrén *wby* system, particularly well-suited to early-type stars.

Vytas Straizys, one-time director of the Vilnius Observatory in Lithuania, and a number of his colleagues, brought their experience of the Stromvil system, optimised for robust classification across all spectral types, even in the presence of interstellar reddening.

Many meetings, and many internal reports, followed over several years. In an early design, considered by Matria Marconi Space at the end of the first industrial study in mid-1998, photometry in four broad bands was obtained from the main astrometric telescopes, along with seven medium-width spectral bands in a third, smaller telescope, with a collecting aperture of $0.75 \times 0.70 \text{ m}^2$.

The next major design iteration, described in depth in the Concept and Technology Study Report in 2000, increased this to 11 intermediate bands. In 2006, this increased again to a total of 19 bands, the details described in a 35-author paper by Jordi et al. (2006).

BUT THINGS CHANGED DRAMATICALLY while the paper was being finalised, with a novel design remaining largely confidential because it was developing during the competitive bid for the industrial contract. Matra Marconi Space (who were eventually assigned the industrial contract), proposed a major overhaul of the design for reasons of operational simplicity, mass and cost.

They proposed to drop the dedicated photometric telescope, and to replace the photometric filters with two low-dispersion prisms. With the detailed involvement and extensive simulations led by Erik Høg, Carme Jordi, Anthony Brown, and Lennart Lindegren, a careful optimisation of the prism properties eventually resulted in the Gaia photometry that we have today.

The resulting focal plane assembly is common to both telescopes, and has five main functions: (a) object detection in the sky mapper; (b) astrometry in the astrometric field; (c) low-resolution spectrophotometry using the blue and red photometers, BP and RP; (d) spectroscopy using the radial-velocity spectrometer; and (e) supporting metrology, comprising both wave-front sensing and basic angle monitoring.

The primary astrometric instrument defines the unfiltered, white-light photometric *G* band, extending over the wavelength range 330–1050 nm. This wide-band photometric data has the highest signal-to-noise, and is therefore most relevant for, e.g., variability studies.

MULTI-COLOUR PHOTOMETRY is finally achieved by two fused-silica prisms, dispersing light entering the fields of view (Gaia et al., 2016). The bandpasses are defined by the optical coatings deposited on the prisms, together with the telescope transmission and detector quantum efficiency.

The prisms, located in the common path of the two telescopes, are mounted on a CCD cold radiator, directly in front of the focal plane. Each are equipped with a strip of seven CCDs, which cover the full astrometric field of view in the across-scan direction. The photometers thus sample the same transits as the astrometric instrument.

The prisms disperse object images in the along-scan direction, spreading them over ~ 45 pixels (at 15 mag), the along-scan window size of 60 pixels allowing for sky background subtraction. The spectral dispersion, which matched the earlier photometric-filter design of Jordi et al. (2006), results from the intrinsic dispersion of fused silica, and varies from 3–27 nm per pixel over the range 330–680 nm for BP, and from 7–15 nm per pixel over the range 640–1050 nm for RP.

For the great majority of objects, the BP and RP spectra are binned on-chip in the across-scan direction, over 12 pixels, to form one-dimensional, along-scan spectra. Unbinned, single-pixel-resolution windows (of size 60×12 pixels²) are only used for stars brighter than $G = 11.5$ mag.

THE DISPERSED SPECTRA overlap in crowded regions. Compared with the astrometric crowding limit of around a million objects per square degree, BP/RP photometry is typically limited to about 750 000 objects per square degree. Above that, window overlap and truncation occurs and, because the onboard detection prioritises bright stars, faint-star completeness is impacted.

Methods used to extend this in even higher density areas of particular scientific importance, in particular Baade's Window in the Galactic centre, and the globular cluster ω Cen, have been developed (Gaia et al., 2016).

ON GROUND, the photometric pipeline processes the data from the sky mappers, the astrometric field, and the BP and RP photometers. The source fluxes in the *G* band (from the astrometric field images) are turned into calibrated epoch photometry in the *G* band.

Integrated fluxes from the BP and RP spectra provide calibrated epoch photometry in G_{BP} and G_{RP} , while the spectra themselves are wavelength and flux calibrated.

The photometric and spectroscopic data are calibrated by means of standard stars for which high-quality, ground-based spectrophotometry has been collected (Pancino et al., 2012). Extended monitoring campaigns furthermore establish the photometric stability of the standard stars (Altavilla et al., 2015).

Today, EDR3 contains 1.806 billion sources with *G*-band photometry, and 1.540 billion with BP and RP photometry (Busso et al., 2021; Riello et al., 2021). The median uncertainty in the *G*-band is 0.2 mmag at $G = 10 - 14$, 0.8 mmag at $G = 17$, and 2.6 mmag at $G = 19$.

DOWNSTREAM in the data processing chain, the variable star processing takes all the epoch photometry, and provides a classification of the variable type and a characterisation of the light curve (Eyer et al., 2014).

The subsequent task of 'astrophysical parameter inference' then analyses the combination of astrometry, photometry, and spectroscopy to derive discrete source classifications (for example, distinguishing single stars, white dwarfs, binaries, quasars, and galaxies), and to infer the astrophysical properties of each source.

Astrophysical parameters derived from the BP and RP data are the effective temperature, surface gravity, metallicity, and extinction (Bailer-Jones et al., 2013). From the RVS spectra of the brightest stars, α -element enhancements and individual elemental abundances can be derived in addition (Recio-Blanco et al., 2016).

The accuracy of the parameter estimates depends on the star's magnitude, and is further constrained by the degeneracy between effective temperature and extinction. As an example, for FGKM stars at $G = 15$ mag with low extinction, effective temperatures can be estimated to 75–250 K, extinction to 0.06–0.15 mag, surface gravities to 0.2–0.5 dex, and metallicity [Fe/H] to 0.1–0.3 dex.